

Network Traffic Intrusion Detection Using Machine Learning

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Abstract—Cybercrime has turned into a business in the digital age. Cyberattacks now result in the loss of sensitive data and significant financial losses for organizations. Consequently, cybersecurity, the expert's job is crucial to safeguarding the data against attacks. Intrusion detection is the main topic of research to identify those mysterious attacks. Machine learning algorithms play a vital role in intrusion detection by precisely identifying threats. Machine learning methods like Decision Tree and SVM are used to cover the detailed analysis of the datasets. It is examined and compared how accurate and precise the provided dataset is.

Keywords—IDS, Machine Learning Techniques, Decision Tree, SVM.

I. INTRODUCTION

An IDS is a security system that keeps an eye on network traffic and computer systems. It examines that traffic for any potential hostile assaults coming from the outside as well as any system abuse or insider attacks. An intrusion detection system is a piece of software that uses a number of machine learning methods to find network intrusions. IDS monitors for harmful activity and prevents users—possibly insiders—from gaining unauthorized access. The demand for more intelligent intrusion detection is growing as we speak since a skilled attacker can get beyond existing barriers. In this field of cyber security, researchers are seeking to use ML approaches. Applying supervised machine learning algorithms to historical alert data can greatly increase classification accuracy and cut down on analysts' research time. It can provide analysts with more information and insights to support their decision-making. Although prediction models built on the basis of past data can increase analyst productivity, they will never completely replace security analysts. The goal is to create a network intrusion detector, a prediction model that can assess the dataset's accuracy and precision.

II. RELATED WORKS

Somaraju Ram Prasad et al. [1] proposed a paper for predicting the intrusion detection using PCA with Random Forest, SVM, Naive bayes and it is given that the better model id PCA with Random Forest Approach.

The Gaussian Naïve-Bayes algorithm yields the fastest training and testing times within the range of 0.12 s to 3.41 s, according to the data is concluded by Johan Note et al. [2].

To do comparative analysis, efficient classification methods such as Support Vector Machine and Naive Bayes have been used and their accuracy and misclassification rate are computed. The outcomes show that SVM improves Naive Bayes. Anish Halimaa A et al. [3]

Another review paper, in which they make research on the IDS using KDDCup99 and its variant NSL-KDD using different machine learning algorithm and they get highest accuracy for Cluster center and nearest neighbor (CANN) with 99.9. SH Kok et al. [4]

A comparison analysis was carried out to evaluate several machine learning algorithms and evaluate their ability to forecast for cyberattacks. The suggested machine learning technique performed exceptionally well according to the data, demonstrating its durability for cyberattack prediction. T. Sanjay et al. [5]

III. METHODOLOGY

The main aim of this system is to analyze and compare the accuracy and precision of the given dataset using two different algorithms.

Fig 1. Flow Chart

A. DATA COLLECTION

The data set used is KDD Cup1999 dataset and this is a network intrusion detection dataset it consists of 42 attributes with the class label such as normal or abnormal. Out of the 42 features/attributes in this data set, 41 attributes can be categorized into 4 different classes namely basic, content, traffic and host features. The value type is either continuous(C)/ discrete(D). The dataset consist of numeric as well as the categorical variables.

Table 1: Feature dataset

Basic/Intrinsic Features:	Content Features	
Duration	hot	num_access_files
protocol_type	num_failed_logins	num_outbound_cmds
service	logged_in	is_hot_login
src_bytes	num_compromised	is_guest_login
dst_bytes	root_shell	count
flag	su_attempted	error_rate
land	num_root	error_rate
wrong_fragment	num_file_creations	same_srv_rate

urgent	num_shells	diff_srv_rate
	srv_count	srv_error_rate
	srv_error_rate	srv_diff_host_rate

Table 2: Feature Dataset

Host Features	
dst_host_count	dst_host_srv_count
dst_host_diff_srv_rate	dst_host_same_srv_rate
dst_host_same_src_port_rate	dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate
dst_host_error_rate	dst_host_srv_error_rate
dst_host_rerror_rate	dst_host_srv_rerror_rate

B. DATA PREPROCESSING

Then we have to import the php-ml in to php by importing autoload.php file. And we can use all the algorithms from the classification directory and can use the Metric functions for calculating the various metrics.

```

require 'vendor/autoload.php';

use Phpml\Classification\DecisionTree;
use Phpml\Classification\SVC;
use Phpml\CrossValidation\RandomSplit;
use Phpml\Dataset\ArrayDataset;
use Phpml\Metric\Accuracy;
use Phpml\Metric\Precision;
use Phpml\Metric\Recall;
    
```

Data cleaning and transformation into a format suitable for training machine learning models are steps in the process of data preprocessing, a fundamental stage in machine learning. Enhancing the quality of the data, handling missing values, encoding categorical variables, scaling numerical features, and carrying out additional procedures that can boost the performance of machine learning models are the objectives of data preparation. some common data preprocessing techniques in machine learning are Remove rows or columns with missing values, convert categorical variables into numerical format, as most machine learning algorithms work with numerical data.

```

if (($handle = fopen($csvFile, 'r')) !== false) {
    while (($row = fgetcsv($handle, 1000, ',')) !== false) {
        $data[] = array_slice($row, 0, -1); // Remove the last column
        $label = end($row); // Get the last column as labels
        if (!isset($labelMapping[$label])) {
            $labelMapping[$label] = count($labelMapping); // Assign
        }
        $labels[] = $labelMapping[$label];
    }
}
    
```

C. TRAIN-TEST SPLIT

Split the dataset into training, validation, and testing sets to evaluate model performance. Common splits are 70/30, 80/20,

or 90/10 for training/validation/testing, respectively. The process of test and train splitting is essential for assessing a model's ability to make accurate predictions on unseen data.

```
// Split the dataset into training and testir
$split = new RandomSplit($dataset, 0.8);
$trainSamples = $split->getTrainSamples();
$trainLabels = $split->getTrainLabels();
$testSamples = $split->getTestSamples();
$testLabels = $split->getTestLabels();
```

IV. MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

The two machine learning algorithms are used. They are SVM and Decision Tree.

A. SVM

```
$svmClassifier = new SVC();
$svmClassifier->train($trainSamples, $trainLabels);
$svmPredictions = $svmClassifier->predict($testSamples);
$svmAccuracy = Accuracy::score($testLabels, $svmPredictions);
```

B. Decision Tree

```
$dtClassifier = new DecisionTree();
$dtClassifier->train($trainSamples, $trainLabels);
$dtPredictions = $dtClassifier->predict($testSamples);
$dtAccuracy = Accuracy::score($testLabels, $dtPredictions);
```

V. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULT

The work is implemented in VS code using php-ml library and the data is collected from Kaggle. Here is an interface to upload the csv file and the data is split into train and test data as 80/20 percentage of dataset. Php-ml allows the model to evaluate and trained using the dataset and the accuracy and precision of the relevant calculated using the algorithms.

We can find the accuracy, precision and recall using confusion matrix, that will give the performance of the dataset.

Accuracy:

The model's accuracy is used for evaluating its performance. It is calculated as the proportion of all accurate instances to all instances.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+TN+TP}$$

Precision:

Precision is a measure of how accurate a model's positive predictions are.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

Recall:

A classification model's recall evaluates how well it finds each relevant instance within a dataset.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

The two algorithms used are SVM and Decision Tree that used to find the highest level of accuracy, each of them is compared and compute the greatest accuracy rate, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: comparison Table

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
SVM	0.937534	0.897784	0.997511
Decision Tree	0.973803	0.980268	0.970870

Fig 2. Result comparison

VI. CONCLUSION

The objective of this research is to use the machine learning classification models to enhances the detection of intrusion detection using network traffic data. In this research we can conclude that the highest accuracy for the IDS is 0.97 for Decision Tree algorithm.

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